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How have economic hardships including inflation, unemployment, declining income, and macroeconomic instability affected turnout in Iran's national elections between 2000 and 2024?

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Table of Contents

1. Introduction	1
2. Theoretical Framework: Economy, Political Evaluation, and the Possibility of Reaction	2
2.1 The Logic of Economic Voting: Individual Experience and National Perception	2
2.2 Clarity of Responsibility and Institutional Structure	2
2.3 The “Voice” and “Exit” Framework	3
2.4 Rentier Economy and Competitive Authoritarianism in Iran	3
3. Economic Transformations and the Reshaping of the Political Competition Landscape (2000–2024)	4
3.1 Macroeconomic Overview of Iran (2000–2024)	4
3.2 Transformations in the Structure of Political Competition	5
3.3 From Periodic Shocks to Structural Pressure	5
4. Trends in Electoral Participation in Iran (2000–2024)	6
5. Has Economic Hardship Led to “Exit”?	7
6. Conclusion	9
7. References	11

1. Introduction

Economic conditions have long been recognized as one of the key determinants shaping political behavior, particularly voter turnout and electoral preferences. The theory of economic voting rests on the assumption that citizens evaluate the economic performance of governments and respond to political actors based on a “reward–punishment” logic; that is, economic prosperity typically increases support for the incumbent government, while economic downturns generally reduce it (Lewis-Beck & Stegmaier, 2007: 518–520). Within this framework, the existing literature distinguishes between two approaches: the pocketbook perspective, which emphasizes individual economic experience, and the sociotropic perspective, which highlights citizens’ overall assessment of national economic conditions (Kinder & Kiewiet, 1981: 129–132).

These models are largely based on consolidated democracies but researches show that in transitional political systems, economic crises can trigger electoral volatility, weaken party systems, and produce sudden shifts in participation patterns (Roberts, 2012: 1424–1428). However in the case of Iran between 2000 and 2024 presents unique institutional and political complexities: the Guardian Council’s vetting mechanisms, the dual structure of power, and factional cleavages they all shape how economic dissatisfaction is translated into electoral participation.

The main research question of this study is therefore:

How have economic hardships including inflation, unemployment, declining income, and macroeconomic instability affected voter turnout in Iran’s national elections between 2000 and 2024?

Using a historical–analytical approach, this article examines four distinct political and economic phases and demonstrates how the shift from “stimulative inflation” to “erosive inflation” has transformed the traditional relationship between livelihoods and political participation. The central argument here is that the economic pressure alone does not necessarily lead to lower turnout; rather, this relationship weakens when citizens lose confidence in the political system’s ability to reform or manage economic crises. Under such conditions, the logic of punitive voting gives way to a structural withdrawal from the electoral process.

2. Theoretical Framework: Economy, Political Evaluation, and the Possibility of Reaction

2.1 The Logic of Economic Voting: Individual Experience and National Perception

The economic voting literature is based on the assumption that citizens evaluate government performance by assessing economic conditions and respond according to a “reward–punishment” logic (Lewis-Beck & Stegmaier, 2007: 518–520). This evaluation can occur at two levels: direct personal economic experience (pocketbook voting) and the overall perception of national economic conditions (sociotropic voting) (Kinder & Kiewiet, 1981: 129–134).

However, empirical studies show that the relationship between economic pressure and electoral reaction is neither linear nor automatic. Personal experience of crisis or corruption may reduce support for the government, but the intensity and direction of this reaction depend on competitive conditions and the public salience of the issue (Klašnja et al., 2014: 67–70). Moreover, economic voting at the national level is often shaped by citizens’ general evaluation of economic performance rather than solely by personal economic experience (Kinder & Kiewiet, 1981: 153–154).

Therefore, economic pressure leads to punitive voting only when citizens can clearly attribute responsibility for current conditions to a specific political actor and when they perceive electoral change as a feasible option.

2.2 Clarity of Responsibility and Institutional Structure

The clarity of responsibility theory argues that voters are able to reward or punish incumbents electorally only when responsibility for economic outcomes is clearly attributable (Powell & Whitten, 1993: 392–401). In the political systems where power is centralized and accountability is transparent, the link between economic evaluation and electoral behavior becomes stronger. When power is dispersed across multiple institutions or when the boundaries of responsibility are ambiguous, this link gets weaker (Anderson, 2000: 151–156; Lewis-Beck & Stegmaier, 2000: 188–190).

In such contexts, economic dissatisfaction does not necessarily generate effective electoral mobilization and it may instead reduce incentives for participation. From this perspective, economic voting is not merely a function of the economic conditions but is also contingent upon citizens’ perceptions of institutional accountability mechanisms.

2.3 The “Voice” and “Exit” Framework

To explain why reactions to economic crises differ, Hirschman’s conceptual framework is particularly useful. Hirschman argues that when actors face decline, they may either attempt to participate in reform through voice (active protest or expression), or disengage from participation through exit (withdrawal) (Hirschman, 1970: 21,30).

The choice between these two pathways depends on different things like citizens’ assessment of their capacity to influence outcomes, the perceived costs of political action, and the level of loyalty to the system. When channels of voice are not effective or blocked, the likelihood of opting for exit increases (Hirschman, 1970: 77–80). With this perspective, declining participation can be understood as a rational response to institutional closure rather than merely as political apathy.

2.4 Rentier Economy and Competitive Authoritarianism in Iran

To apply this framework to Iran, it is necessary to account for the structural characteristics of both its economy and political system. Rentier state theory emphasizes that in economies that are dependent on oil revenues, the state being the primary recipient of rent plays a central role in resource distribution and in sustaining political legitimacy (Beblawi, 1987: 384–387). During periods of resource abundance, this distributive capacity can help manage social dissatisfaction; however, declines in oil exports and constraints on foreign exchange reserves weaken this material foundation of legitimacy.

At the same time, Iran’s political structure can be understood within the framework of competitive authoritarianism, where elections are held but competition is not fully equal, and unelected institutions can restrict the scope of electoral contestation (Levitsky & Way, 2010: 16–17). The combination of a rentier economy and institutional ambiguity in accountability makes it difficult for citizens to attribute economic outcomes to a specific political actor, and it weakens the potential for punitive voting.

In these contexts, persistent economic crisis may increase the likelihood of a shift from voice to exit, rather than strengthening patterns of punitive voting.

3. Economic Transformations and the Reshaping of the Political Competition Landscape (2000–2024)

3.1 Macroeconomic Overview of Iran (2000–2024)

Over the past two decades, Iran's economy has been characterized by structural instability, dependence on oil, and also vulnerability to external shocks. Three major waves of the sanctions (2006, 2012, and 2018) have played a decisive role in intensifying this instability.

Inflation during this period has remained chronically high. The World Bank attributes this persistence to rising inflation expectations and the government's reliance on deficit financing (World Bank, 2025: 1). The analyses by the International Monetary Fund show that reduced oil exports, growth in the monetary base, and depreciation of the exchange rate had significant relationships with inflation (IMF, 2022: 12–14).

Following the implementation of the JCPOA, a brief period of relative stability emerged in 2016–2017, marked by high economic growth and declining inflation (IMF, 2018: 1). However the United States' withdrawal from the agreement in 2018 pushed the economy into deep stagflation, with inflation surpassing 40 percent (IMF, 2022: 3). Between 2018 and 2019 the economy contracted by more than 10 percent (Heni, 2025: 13–14).

The labor market has also suffered from structurally persistent unemployment. While official unemployment rates have hovered around 10–12 percent, youth unemployment especially among women has reached significantly higher levels in some years (Salehi-Isfahani: 11–12). Research also confirms the presence of hysteresis in Iran's labor market (Unemployment Hysteresis in Iran: 1–2).

Simultaneously, the size of the middle class has declined since 2012, a trend that accelerated after 2018 (Farzanegan & Habibi, 2025: 15–18). High inflation and declining real wages have eroded household purchasing power, contributing to chronic welfare deterioration (Farzanegan & Habibi, 2025: 6–7).

Overall, Iran's economy has not merely passed through periodic cycles of crisis but has entered a stage of chronic erosion a condition that carries fundamental implications for understanding electoral behavior.

3.2 Transformations in the Structure of Political Competition

The economic developments outlined above unfolded alongside significant shifts in the structure of electoral competition. During the final years of the reform era (2001–2005), voter turnout remained comparatively high reaching 77.24 percent in the 2001 presidential election and 82.63 percent in the 2000 parliamentary elections (International IDEA, 2022) reflecting strong mobilization of the urban middle classes (Kamrava, 2010: 402–403). These years were characterized by relatively high and broad-based growth (IMF, 2003: 6), preceding the political realignment that followed the 2005 election.

With the rise of the Ahmadinejad administration, redistributive policies relying on oil revenues intensified, while inflationary and currency instability increased simultaneously (Mahmoud/Masoodnia, 2024: 1). The 2009 election and the subsequent protests represented a turning point in the widening gap between society and the political system (Kamrava, 2010: 400–401).

The period from 2013 to 2017 was marked by the nuclear agreement and the high economic growth of 2016 (around 7.4 percent) (IMF, 2017: 5). It brought a temporary return of political competition and renewed public hope. However, the reimposition of sanctions in 2018, subsequent stagflation, and the severe depreciation of the rial once again reshaped the political landscape (IMF, 2022, 6–7, 10; Kamrava, 2010: 406–407).

From 2019 onward, amid sustained economic pressure and increasingly restricted electoral competition (Freedom House, 2022–2023; IDEA), voter turnout fell to its lowest historical levels.

3.3 From Periodic Shocks to Structural Pressure

What distinguishes Iran's economy during this period is its gradual transition from episodic external shocks to prolonged structural strain. As documented by the (World Bank, 2020: ix–xi, 1), consecutive recessions following the 2012 and 2018 sanctions shocks, persistent high inflation, exchange rate depreciation, and historically low oil revenues contributed to a decade-long stagnation, reshaping expectations about economic stability and predictability.

The World Bank reports that in the past decade, millions have fallen below the poverty line, and real consumption among lower-income deciles has declined (World Bank, 2020: 15–19). This continuous erosion of welfare has deepened feelings of economic insecurity. Under such circumstances, economic pressure is no longer merely a short-term variable but has become part of citizens' everyday lived experience. This transformation provides the analytical basis for examining how patterns of electoral response have changed over time.

4. Trends in Electoral Participation in Iran (2000–2024)

The electoral participation in Iran has been through significant changes over the past two decades, which reflects the interaction between economic conditions, the structure of political competition, and public trust in the effectiveness of electoral institutions. Although presidential and parliamentary elections are institutionally different, they exhibit complementary trends in this regard. Presidential elections have typically been associated with heightened political polarization and broader mobilization, whereas parliamentary elections have generally been viewed as indicators of the level of genuine competition and institutional legitimacy.

During the 2000s, voter turnout in parliamentary elections displayed moderate but meaningful fluctuations. In the post-1997 reformist atmosphere, turnout in the 2000 parliamentary elections reached approximately 67 percent (Portal Data Iran). As the scope of competition narrowed and candidate disqualifications increased in the 2004 and 2008 parliamentary elections, voter turnout fell sharply to roughly 50 percent declining to 50.57 percent in 2004 and 49.47 percent in 2008 (IDEA). In the 2016 elections, coinciding with the post-JCPOA environment and a partial return of political competition, turnout again rose to around 60 percent (Frazan, 2016). However, the 2020 parliamentary elections marked a turning point, with participation falling to about 42 percent the lowest level in the history of parliamentary elections up to that time (Azizi 2020). This trend continued in the 2024 elections, and says that for a significant portion of society the parliament is no longer perceived as an effective institution for producing political or economic change.

Presidential elections have followed a similar but more volatile trajectory. Between 2001–2009 and 2013–2017, high voter turnout corresponded with the perception that political change and economic improvement were still possible. During these periods, elections were widely seen as a meaningful mechanism for influencing policy. The 2009 presidential election, though marked by high turnout, was followed by widespread protests, demonstrating that segments of society continued to use electoral participation as a channel for expressing political dissatisfaction (Kamrava, 2010: 408–410). At this stage, the logic of “intra-system protest” remained active.

However, from 2019 onward, a different pattern emerged. Amid chronic stagflation, currency depreciation,

and increasingly restricted political competition (IMF, 2022: 6-7), turnout in the 2020 parliamentary elections and the 2021 presidential election reached historically low levels (IDEA 2022). Unlike previous cycles, neither significant turnover in power nor broad protest mobilization occurred; instead, electoral disengagement intensified.

Overall, trends in voter turnout from 2000 to 2024 show that electoral behavior in Iran has not been shaped merely by economic fluctuations. Rather, it has become increasingly linked to citizens' evaluations of the effectiveness of electoral mechanisms and the degree of political competition. The conjunction of sustained economic pressure with a shrinking competitive arena has facilitated a shift from electoral mobilization toward reduced participation.

5. Has Economic Hardship Led to “Exit”?

Electoral participation in Iran has reached its lowest historical levels since 2019. This decline has coincided with chronic inflation, currency depreciation, and consecutive periods of negative economic growth (IMF, 2022 :6-7, IDEA, 2022). However, the simultaneity of these trends is not sufficient to establish causality. To explain this relationship, it is necessary to show through which mechanisms economic hardship has reshaped citizens' political perceptions and altered their electoral behavior.

Within the framework of economic voting, citizens evaluate governmental performance based on their assessment of economic conditions and, when evaluations are negative, shift their support toward alternative options (Lewis-Beck & Stegmaier, 2007: 518–520). Moreover, sociotropic assessments citizens' evaluations of the overall national economy often exert a stronger effect than purely personal economic experiences (Kinder & Kiewiet, 1981: 129–134). In Iran, prior to 2017, economic dissatisfaction largely manifested through punitive voting and alternation between political factions. However, after the reimpositioning of sanctions and the entrenchment of stagflation, the economic crisis has shifted from a cyclical condition to a more persistent and erosive one. In this context, negative evaluations were no longer directed solely at the incumbent administration but increasingly generalized to the perceived effectiveness of the electoral system itself. Thus, the classical mechanism of electoral punishment weakened.

A second mechanism of influence concerns the gradual erosion of the middle class. OECD reports indicate that slow income growth and rising job insecurity can undermine the economic position of the middle class (OECD, 2019: 13–16).

In Iran, the IMF has highlighted the combination of the weak non-oil growth, high inflation, and currency volatility, which all of them have exerted substantial pressure on real household incomes (IMF, 2022: 5–7). The middle class historically one of the key drivers of electoral participation has lost part of its political mobilization capacity as purchasing power has declined and economic uncertainty has deepened. Under such conditions, electoral participation may appear less impactful or less of a priority.

A third mechanism can be understood through the lens of rentier state theory. In oil-dependent economies, the state maintains a link between economic benefits and political legitimacy through resource distribution (Beblawi, 1987: 384–387). Declining oil exports and limited foreign exchange reserves have weakened the state's distributive capacity a trend the IMF has linked to reduced oil revenues and inflationary pressures (IMF, 2022: 5–7). As this material foundation of legitimacy erodes, the connection between electoral participation and economic benefit becomes increasingly fragile.

In light of these dynamics, a historical comparison of voter responses shows that economic pressure has not always led to declining participation in Iran. In periods when elections were still perceived as effective tools of change, economic dissatisfaction translated into punitive voting, as evidenced in the 2005, 2013, and 2017 elections. Even in 2009, high turnout combined with widespread protests indicated that the logic of voice within the system (Hirschman, 1970: 29–30) remained active (Kamrava, 2010: 406–410). However, since 2019, as economic pressure has become entrenched (IMF, 2022: 6–7) and political competition more restricted, a different pattern has emerged. Voter turnout has fallen to its lowest levels (IDEA, 2022), while neither significant power shifts nor widespread protest mobilizations have occurred.

Within Hirschman's conceptual framework, this shift can be interpreted as a transition from voice to exit a situation in which citizens, lacking a perception of political efficacy, rationally choose electoral withdrawal (Hirschman, 1970: 77–80).

In sum, economic hardship in Iran has not merely increased individual dissatisfaction; it has reshaped political behavior through the weakening of electoral punishment mechanisms, the erosion of the middle class, and the diminished distributive capacity of the state. What has changed is not simply the level of economic pressure but the perceived possibility of change through elections. In this context, electoral exit is not a sign of apathy but a reflection of a transformed relationship between the economy, legitimacy, and political effectiveness.

6. Conclusion

This study by asking how economic hardship electoral participation in Iran between 2000 and 2024, demonstrates that the relationship between economic conditions and voter turnout is neither linear nor uniform. Economic pressures have produced different forms of political response across time: in some periods, they generated punitive mobilization and shifts in executive power; in others, they fueled intra-system protest; and in the recent years, they have contributed to declining turnout and electoral disengagement. Thus, economic hardship alone does not determine levels of participation; rather, citizens' reactions to such pressures depend on their perceptions of political efficacy and the degree to which elections are viewed as meaningful avenues for change.

The causal analysis shows that the shift from punitive voting to exit cannot be explained solely through classical theories of economic voting. As the economic crisis evolved from a cyclical downturn into a chronic and structural condition, negative evaluations were no longer directed only at the incumbent administration but extended to the entire policy-making process. In this environment, elections themselves not merely the prospects of changing the government became objects of doubt concerning political effectiveness.

At the same time, the gradual erosion of the middle class, declining purchasing power, job insecurity, and the shrinking distributive capacity of the rentier state weakened the link between economic interests and political participation (Beblawi, 1987: 384–387). Falling oil revenues and inflationary pressures further intensified this dynamic (IMF, 2022: 5–7). Under such conditions, what changed was not only the level of dissatisfaction but citizens' broader assessment of the possibility of intra-systemic reform.

Within Hirschman's conceptual framework, this transformation can be interpreted as a shift from voice to exit (Hirschman, 1970: 1–6, 77–80). The decline in electoral participation in recent years is not necessarily a sign of political apathy; rather, it may represent a rational response to a situation in which the costs of participation are high and the perceived likelihood of political influence is low. From this perspective, electoral exit is not passivity but an indication of a changing relationship between the economy, legitimacy, and perceptions of political effectiveness.

The findings of this research suggest that in semi-competitive and rentier systems, persistent economic crisis can alter the traditional relationship between dissatisfaction and political mobilization.

When elections are not perceived as effective mechanisms of change, economic pressure does not lead to protest voting but instead to political disengagement. Therefore, the recent decline in voter turnout in Iran should be understood not merely as a consequence of recession or inflation but as the outcome of a structural transformation in citizens' perceptions of political efficacy.

Ultimately, the analysis of the 2000–2024 period shows that electoral participation in Iran has followed cycles of economic–political hope and disappointment. A return to higher levels of participation will not depend solely on improved macroeconomic indicators; it will also require the reconstruction of institutional trust and the restoration of public belief in the possibility of change through elections. Until this perception is repaired, the logic of exit may remain the dominant mode of political response.

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